

DEVELOPMENT OF A MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF THE PROCESS OF CAPTURE OF FLAT PRODUCTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6369659>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st March 2022

Accepted: 10th March 2022

Online: 14th March 2022

KEY WORDS

capture, pneumo, suckers, throttle, material, surface.

ABSTRACT

Taking into account the peculiarities of control and management of industrial activity and technological production processes in the developed countries of the world, the concepts of development of scientific and technological progress in Uzbekistan determine the widespread use of modern technologies in the development of high-performance reliable energy-saving technological equipment in all industries. In the world, close attention is paid to solving the complex scientific and technical problem of ensuring the required level of reliability and reliability of information, the development and implementation of methods for ensuring them. However, the principles of automation of actuators and their application in production remain virtually unchanged. Increasing productivity and reducing the cost of manufacturing products determines the need for enterprises in technological equipment based on fundamentally new methods. However, the gap between the achievements of the developers of new non-traditional methods, devices, methods and their mass introduction into production is currently increasing.

INTRODUCTION

The degree of rarefaction in the central part of the pneumatic gripper depends on a variety of device parameters. To determine the possibility of their increase, the development of appropriate mathematical models is required.

In the central part of the suction cup, which is the supporting surface of the pneumatic gripper, a rarefaction R_{vac} is created.

As you know, in practice, the real surface is not absolutely even. Therefore, in the process of gripping, gaps are formed between the surfaces of the sheet material and the suction cup, allowing air particles to pass through, which negatively affects the actual load capacity.

One of the main criteria for pneumatic gripping is its carrying capacity.

The lifting force F arising in the capture zone can be determined:

$$F = F_n + F_c = P_{\text{бак}} f_n + \int_{f_c} p df_c,$$

RESEARCH METHODS

Where, F_n, F_c - constituent parts of the lifting force, which are created in the area limited by the walls of the annular channel and the joint area; f_i - gripping surface area bounded by the walls of the annular channel; f_c - joint surface area; $p(r)$ - pressure distribution in the joint channel in the radial direction.

In order to reduce the throttling of air passing through the hole, when designing a gripping device (GD), the width of the annular channel should be chosen as large as possible (Fig. 1). This leads to a decrease

in the joint surface area and when determining the lifting force F .

If we read the distribution of rarefaction P_{vac} in the radial direction along the annular channel, we consider it constant, then the force F is determined by the formula:

$$F = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{r_{e1}}^{r_{c1}} P_{\text{вак}} r dr d\alpha = \pi(r_{c1}^2 - r_{e1}^2) P_{\text{вак}}$$

Where, r_{c1}, r_{e1} - respectively, the radii of the outer and inner walls of the annular channel..

Fig.1. Scheme for determining the static load rating for products with a small gripping area

Rice. 2 Jet flow when gripping the workpiece (ZU - gripping device of aerodynamic action; VK - vortex channel)

With a symmetrical arrangement of the joint surfaces, the required volume of flow Q_{min} , which provides the specified load capacity of the charger after gripping flat products:

Where, $A = \pi / (\mu_g P_H)$; μ - coefficient of absolute viscosity of air; P_H - pressure on the outside of the joint; $R_H = (r_{0H} - r_{06}) / (r_{c1} - r_{e1})$; r_{a1}, r_{a2} - respectively, the radii of the outer and inner surfaces of the product.

$$Q = \frac{Ac(P_H^2)}{\ln(R_H)}$$

With a rotational air flow in the central part of the suction cup, a pressure drop (rarefaction) occurs and a force field arises on the surface of the product, as a result of which capture occurs.

With a coaxial location of the captured object, the lifting force of the gripping device is determined by integrating the distribution of the rarefaction value $P_v(r)$ over the surface of the product:

$$F_z = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{r_{\text{os}}}^{r_{\text{oh}}} P_g(r) dr d\alpha$$

To determine the lifting force acting on the surface of the product from the side of the gripping device, it is sufficient and necessary to know the shape of the suction flow and the dependence of the law of change in rarefaction to the supporting surface of the gripping device.

Consider the case in which air is sucked in through a central annular nozzle located parallel to the working surface (Fig. 5). Since the axis of the products coincides with the axis of the central nozzle, the static pressure on the surface of the captured object is symmetrical with respect to the axis of the gripping device. Assuming that the velocity V_B and the pressure P_B in the jet in the plane of the nozzle exit are distributed uniformly on the inner boundary of the jet, and the velocity V_B , respectively, the air flow rate $Q = V_B \delta$, remain constant along the length of the jet, then the momentum equation for such a flow will take the form:

$$\rho V_g^2 \delta = (P_H - P_B) z_1$$

Where, ρ - air density; δ - vacuum annular channel width; P_H - pressure at the outer boundary of the jet; z_1 — distance from the supporting surface of the gripping device to the working surface of the gripping.

The law of conservation of energy, written in the form of the Bernoulli equation:

$$P_H - P_{\text{osk}} = P_H - P_B + \frac{\rho V_g^2}{2}$$

Where, P_{osk} - pressure (vacuum) supplied to the annular channel.

Solving equations (5) and (6), we obtain:

$$P_B = P_H - \frac{2\delta(P_H - P_{\text{osk}})}{2\delta + z_1} \quad (7)$$

The ratio of pressure (vacuum) in the gripping area of the memory device to the total pressure (vacuum) supplied to the annular channel characterizes the pressure coefficient and is determined:

$$\bar{p}_g = \frac{P_H - P_B}{P_H - P_{\text{osk}}} = \frac{1}{1 + z_1/2\delta} = \frac{1}{1 + 0,5\bar{z}_1} \quad (8)$$

Where, $\bar{z}_1 = z_1/\delta$ - dimensionless product position factor.

In the nozzle exit plane, in the direction from the outer edge to the inner one, the air velocity decreases from V_H to V_B , and the static pressure changes from the outer P_H to the P_B pressure at the inner jet boundary. Therefore, the average air velocity at the inlet to the vacuum annular channel will be higher than the value V_B assumed by us, which means that the value obtained by formula (8) will have a slightly overestimated value. The error will decrease as the value decreases, which is quite acceptable, since the capture of the product occurs at small values of the distance from the memory to the product, that is, $\bar{z}_1 < 1 (z_1 < \delta)$

By analogy with [79], one can obtain the flow coefficient and the annular chamber:

$$\mu = \frac{V_B \delta}{V_H \delta} = \sqrt{1 - \bar{p}_B} = \sqrt{\frac{\bar{z}_1}{2 + \bar{z}_1}} \quad (9)$$

The volumetric flow rate of air passing through the vacuum annular channel is determined by:

$$Q = \mu\pi(r_{c1}^2 - r_{e1}^2) \sqrt{\frac{2(P_H - P_{\text{vac}})}{\rho}} \quad (10)$$

According to dependence (4), the distribution of rarefaction in the radial direction on the surface of the product is assumed to be constant and equal to the pressure P_v , then the lifting force is estimated as follows:

$$F_z = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{r_{o6}}^{r_{oH}} P_v(r) dr d\alpha = \pi(r_{oH}^2 - r_{o6}^2) P_B \quad (11)$$

The performance of the gripping device is determined by the time of the gripping process.

According to Fig. 2, the following forces act on the products: $m g$ — product weight force; $F_z = (z)$ - force acting on the product, arising due to the static pressure (vacuum) distributed over its surface, forming a suction effect.

To move and load production products, you must set the speed $V_z = dz/(dt)$.

Under the action of applied forces, the differential equation of motion can be written:

$$m \frac{d^2 z}{dt^2} + F_z(z) - mg = 0,$$

or, denoting $K_2^2 = F_z/(mz)$, we finally get:

$$\frac{d^2 z}{dt^2} + K_2^2 z - g = 0, \quad (12)$$

Where, K_2 — coefficient that determines the speed of movement of the captured object of production.

The solution of equation (12), when substituting the previously obtained value $F_z(z)$ from expression (11), allows us to determine the desired function $z(t)$, which will describe the law of motion of the product in the process of its capture.

Thus, having the solution of the equation in the form and the solution of equation (12) in the form of $z(t)$, one can obtain the time t_3 of the direct capture of the object at the second stage. Then the resulting capture time will be

$$t_{p3} = t_y + t_3 \quad (13)$$

For carrying products during their loading, removal, it is necessary to create high-performance, versatile and reliable automatic devices.

The most promising devices for these purposes are automatic manipulators. Manipulator grippers are one of the main parts of robotic systems.

However, for manipulators with vacuum grippers, in addition to the high-pressure pneumatic network, it is necessary to have special vacuum pumps or a centralized fore-vacuum line to create a vacuum in the suction cup.

Figure 3 shows a schematic diagram of a pneumovortex gripper.

Fig.3. Schematic diagram of a pneumatic vortex gripper.

The pneumatic vortex gripper consists of a hollow body 1, in which a vortex chamber 2 is installed with tangentially arranged holes - nozzles 3. A cylindrical branch pipe 4 is attached to the body, forming an annular gap 5 with the inner diameter of the vortex chamber.

Coaxial to the vortex chamber there is a cylindrical branch pipe 6 for air outlet, made in diameter larger than the diameter of the branch pipe 4. A rubber cuff 7 is attached to the lower part of the housing for sucking parts.

The operation of the pneumatic vortex gripper is carried out as follows.

Compressed air enters through tangential holes - nozzles into the cavity of the chamber 2. The rotating flow in the zone of the cavity of the branch pipe 4 creates a rarefaction, due to which air will be injected from the atmosphere into the cavity of the branch pipe, which contributes to the appearance of the aerodynamic effect of attraction. When bringing the gripper, for example, to a stack of sheet material, the top sheet will be lifted up from a certain distance and pressed against the end face of the gripper. The most characteristic parameters that affect the magnitude of the suction force

are the structural elements of the grip and the flow parameters.

The experiment was carried out by simultaneously varying the design and pneumatic parameters of the grip.

The main design dimensions of the pneumatic vortex gripper were chosen according to previous studies (Chapter 3, Clause 1).

The effect of the diameter and angle of inclination of the nozzle holes on the degree of rarefaction was determined. The dependences of the pressure drop on the diameter of the holes - nozzles and the suction force on the inlet pressure are obtained.

Figure 4 shows the results of a study of the influence of the diameter of holes - nozzles on the pressure drop. As can be seen from the graphs, the maximum pressure drop in the cavity of the cylindrical branch pipe with a vortex chamber diameter $D_k = 8.2$ mm, a cylindrical branch pipe diameter $d_p = 6.2$ mm and an annular gap $\Delta 3 = 0.5$ mm was obtained at a diameter holes - nozzles $d_c = 2.5 \div 3.0$ mm. In addition, it was found that the largest value of ΔP occurs at the angle of inclination of the axis of the nozzle holes to the axis of the vortex chamber $\alpha = 5^\circ$. In this case, the end of the branch pipe was set at a distance $l_1 = 3.0$ mm

Fig.4. Influence of orifice diameter - nozzles on pressure drop.

- - at inlet pressure $P_{ex}=0,5$ MPa, $\alpha=5^\circ$;
- - at inlet pressure $P_{ex}=0,5$ MPa, $\alpha=0^\circ$;
- △ - at inlet pressure $P_{ex}=0,3$ MPa, $\alpha=0^\circ$.

The ratio of the diameters of nozzles 4 and 6 was taken

$$\frac{d_n}{D_1} = 0,5.$$

The change in the value of the suction force from the inlet pressure is shown in Fig.5. As can be seen from the graph, with an increase in inlet pressure, the suction force increases, therefore, the load capacity increases.

However, it should be noted that an increase in inlet pressure above $P_{in}>0.4$ MPa leads to an increase in noise, so it is

recommended to work at an inlet pressure not exceeding $P_{in}\leq 0.4$ MPa.

The gripper response time at inlet pressure $P_{in}=0.3$ MPa is $0.2\div 0.25$ s. The value of the lifting capacity of the capture is regulated by a smooth change in the inlet pressure.

On the basis of the research carried out, a pneumatic vortex gripper was developed for mass-produced automatic manipulators (industrial robots) PR RF-201M. Figure 6 shows a general view of an automatic manipulator equipped with pneumatic vortex grippers.

Fig.5. Grip force dependence from inlet pressure at different diameters of holes - nozzles.

- - at $d_c=3,0$ mm, $n=3$, $\alpha=5^\circ$;
- - at $d_c=2,0$ mm, $n=3$, $\alpha=5^\circ$.

Technical characteristics of the pilot-industrial gripper of pneumo-vortex action: Compressed air working no more 0,4 pressure, MPa

Compressed air no more 0,35 consumption, m^3/min .

Capture response time, s 0,2÷0,25

load capacity, N before 70

Capture weight, kg 0,2

Industrial tests of pneumovortex grippers showed high reliability of its operation. They are easy to manufacture, easy to use, economical and have a wide range of gripping slabs.

The theoretical and experimental studies carried out have made it possible to develop a number of designs for vacuum grippers. Let's look at some of them

Fig.6. General view of the automatic manipulator, equipped with pneumatic vortex grippers.

1 - RF-201M manipulator; 2 - pneumovortex grippers. 3 - product.

2 CONCLUSION

1. In industry, for the occasional pumping of acids, alkalis, volatile liquids (gasoline, alcohol, ether, etc.) and other aggressive chemical reagents, pumps are required with a simple design of working bodies, quick preparation for start-up with frequent stops, characterized by simplicity service.

2. Due to the high vacuum capacity of the developed aerodynamic vacuum pump, it

can be used for pumping chemical aggressive reagents, suction of emery dust from the grinding wheel, cleaning work areas from chips, etc.

3. For manipulators with vacuum grippers, in addition to the high-pressure pneumatic network, it is necessary to have special vacuum pumps or a centralized fore-vacuum line to create a vacuum in the suction cup

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